

25 The quality of food is determined by different aspects as: quantity and quality of nutrients they
26 contain and the quality and health safety. But what will determine the acceptance or rejection of it is
27 related to the subjective perception of consumers, i. e. aspects related to the preference of color, taste,
28 texture, consistency, presentation, etc. of the product (1), (2).

29 Sensory analysis is a multidisciplinary science that human panelists use the senses of sight, smell,
30 taste, touch and hearing to measure the sensory characteristics and acceptability of foodstuffs and
31 other different materials (3), (4). There is no other instrument that can reproduce or replace human
32 response; therefore, the sensory evaluation is an essential factor in any study of foods. Sensory
33 analysis is applicable in many sectors, such as product development and improvement, quality
34 control, storage studies and process development (5), (6). Good examples are the tendency to reduce
35 the content of salt, sugar substitute, artificial sweeteners or eliminate trans fats for reasons related to
36 health (7), (8), (9), (10). In this case, the investigation was intended to determine whether the
37 sensation produced by food prepared in induction cooker is different from the sensation produced by
38 the same food prepared in LPG based cookers. Test of sensory discrimination is a great tool to
39 evaluate the difference after thermal processing.

40 The microbiological analysis of food is very important to evaluate the content of pathogenic
41 microorganisms and to verify if different cooking processes are determining whether or not to get
42 food fit for consumption (11), (12), (13). In this paper it has been studied the proposed reduction in
43 the number of pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms after heat treatment between samples made
44 with induction and LPG based cookers. Furthermore it is interesting to study the denaturation of food
45 to know if people are taking the necessary nutrients degraded or are taking food without proper
46 nutritional values (11), (13), (14). Finally, it has been desired to know the chemical composition of
47 food made with different cooking instruments.

48 Indoor air quality (IAQ) can be affected by gases (including carbon monoxide, radon, volatile
49 organic compounds), particulates, microbial contaminants (mold, bacteria), or any mass or energy

50 stressor that can induce adverse health conditions. IAQ in Ecuadorian kitchens is poor due to the lack
51 of ventilation and poor air circulation. Source control, filtration and the use of ventilation to dilute
52 contaminants are the primary methods for improving indoor air quality in most buildings (15), (16).

53 In recent years, concerns over the IAQ have increased as a result of knowledge about the
54 significance of air quality and thermal conditions on health, comfort and productivity. Several
55 researchers have been performed in order to evaluate the reduction of greenhouse gases and
56 concentration of carcinogenic compounds emissions in different cookers during cooking. Indoor levels
57 of particles in developed countries are much lower than in developing countries, and this is generally
58 attributable to the advancement in technology for general household activities and also the use of
59 cleaner fuels (such as liquefied petroleum gas, electricity and natural gas) for cooking and heating (17),
60 (18).

61 One of the most dangerous gases is carbon monoxide. Potential sources inside a building that may
62 generate carbon monoxide include gas heating systems, gas stoves, gas hot water heaters, cigarette
63 smoke, and portable kerosene heaters (19), (20). Levels greater than 5 parts per million (ppm) may
64 indicate the presence of exhaust gases in the indoor environment and should be investigated. Levels of
65 carbon monoxide inside buildings should not exceed 9 or 10 ppm (19), (21). Another important gas is
66 carbon dioxide. Properly ventilated buildings should have carbon dioxide levels between 600 ppm and
67 1000 ppm (22), (23). In order to solve this issue, new technologies are being used to offer a solution
68 for clean cooking. Electricity is part of the solution to achieve clean cooking (23), (24). This study
69 investigated the effect of a LPG based cooker, an electric resistance cooker and an induction cooker,
70 under an exhaust hood during cooking case-study dishes of eight Cuisines of Ecuador. Concentrations
71 of CO and CO₂ have been measured in hood idle or working mode during cooking conditions, to
72 evaluate the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions in an Ecuadorian kitchen.

73 South America and especially Ecuador has one of the highest levels of solar radiation and pluviosity
74 worldwide, which could be harvested for supplying the region with adequate access to energy.

75 Furthermore, Ecuador is currently building an infrastructure of 3980 MW to use its vast hydropower
76 resource. In this way, it will be able to substitute renewable energy for fossil fuels in its energy mix.
77 The principal use of this new hydroelectric energy will be to develop the “efficient cooking plan”,
78 which aims the migration from LPG based cookers to electric induction cookers. Cooking is an
79 important part of daily food preparation in commercial and residential settings. In developed countries,
80 the energy required to produce food is still significantly greater than the energy provided by the end-
81 product and constitutes 8-16 % of the total national annual energy consumption (25), From a policy
82 perspective, improvements in all aspects of global food production are necessary to perform
83 sustainable energy practices. Although cooking is only one aspect of food production, it is essential
84 for the safety of food products and contributes to the digestion, micronutrients and acceptability of
85 food (26).

86 In many developing countries, the high costs of modern cooking energy LPG and electricity and
87 their cooking stoves are major constraints for household fuel preferences (27), There are numerous
88 econometric studies on residential energy demand based on time series data (27), or studies (28);
89 however, none of them had been analyzed this issue in Ecuador. Evaluation of renewable energies, and
90 cooking energy costs and efficiencies, using common cooking energy sources as LPG and electricity,
91 and common food items such as water, oil, rice are necessary to know the impact of the energy policy
92 in the cooking energy sector (29).

93 Currently Ecuador is developing the “National Efficient Cooking Program” (NECP), which aims
94 the migration of 3 million of liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), based cookers to electric induction
95 cookers, in order to enhance the security of energy supply and reduce emissions of greenhouse gases
96 and other pollutants (25), (26). In the scope of the NECP currently, the government of Ecuador
97 subsidizes the LPG. In fact, 15 kg of LPG costs \$1,60; on the contrary, in neighbor countries this price
98 is ten or twelve times higher (\$16 and \$20) (30).. This means that the total cost of this subsidy for the
99 country is about 690 dollar millions per year and the total cost caused by smuggling around 20 %. In

100 addition, about 78% of domestic demand for LPG is imported, which creates dependency and therefore
101 a significant outflow of funds abroad that affect the balance of trade in Ecuador.

102 In this context, cooking is an important part of daily food preparation in commercial and residential
103 settings. The application of heat alters the composition of food products to enhance taste, texture,
104 digestibility and shelf-life (27), (28). Although, cooking is only one aspect of food production, it is
105 essential for the safety of food products and contributes to the digestion, micronutrients and
106 acceptability of food (29), (30). In this research, it has been monitored the temperature, time, electrical
107 grid parameters, in order to determine the different stages of cooking, times of cooking in the different
108 dishes, the energy consumption and the cost to the user.

109

110 **2. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD**

111 Quito is the capital of Ecuador, which is about 2800 meters above sea level. Consequently, it is a
112 perfect place to investigate the indoor environment in an Andean place or highland during cooking.
113 For this reason the water boils at 92° C. Culinary laboratories of the Universidad Internacional del
114 Ecuador (UIDE) were selected for taking part of the experiment. No open chimney or other sources of
115 air pollution were found nearby. The studied hood, range and appliances are the typical used in a
116 restaurant kitchen and it has a volume flow rate of 1,2 m³/s. The geometric data of this case-study
117 kitchen are listed in Figure 1. To perform these tests, exterior windows and interior door in the kitchen
118 remained closed in order to avoid the exhausted air flowing back into the kitchen and it could make
119 the stove flamer flutter which affects the burning efficiency. The most important reason for closing the
120 window and interior door is for assuring the accurate measurement of the pollutants concentration. In
121 this study, it was assumed that the primary air would flow from the crack under the interior doors, with
122 a height of 0,02 m from the floor. The front lower edge of the hood of the case-study kitchen overhang
123 is set to 1,8 m as measured vertically from the finished floor.

124 The dishes were cooked using three kind of cookers described as follow:

125 1) An electric induction cooker of four induction zones, two of 18 cm of diameter, one of
126 14,5 cm of diameter and the last one of 21 cm of diameter. The nominal power of this
127 device is 7400 W and the nominal voltage of operation is 220 V. However, for the test
128 only one induction zone was used.

129 2) An industrial LPG cooker SILKO ECG74E of 15000 W. As this LPG cooker is industrial
130 equipment, during the test the power of the cooker burners were limited to 3200 W in order
131 to simulate a domestic cooker. This was made by weighting the difference of the gas
132 cylinder on the laboratory scale, when the controls of the cooker were at different marks,
133 in order to simulate similar conditions to those obtained with the induction cooker.

134 3) The electric cooker used for tests has two burners with a nominal power of 500 W. The
135 cooker characteristics have a direct influence on the test duration, although it was not
136 taken into account when changing any parameter within standards applied to food.

137 The following experiments were conducted using the observational method applied to one kind of
138 induction pot and one induction pan made of AISI 304 stainless steel in their body and AISI 430
139 stainless steel in their bottom which is the normal configuration of induction cookware. Each cookware
140 was covered with an AISI 304 stainless steel lid during the tests.

141

142 ***2.1. Case-study dishes and site selection***

143 The dishes prepared in this study were chosen considering the culinary habits of the Ecuadorian
144 population, chemical composition (macro and micronutrients), microbiological safety and easy to
145 prepare. The cooked dishes were: hard-boiled egg, grilled chicken, milk, boiled chochos (*Lupinus*
146 *mutabilis*), steamed fish, boiled broccoli, little orange (*Solanum quitoense*) with oatmeal drink, and
147 Russian salad which has been composed of boiled carrots, potatoes and peas.

148 The quantity of food was designed to serve lunch for a family between four to six members, except
149 for milk and chochos that were considered for one people. Achiote oil was used as cooking oil. All
150 ingredients and condiments were purchased from a local supermarket, and the amounts used were
151 measured. In order to have the best control of consistency the experiments were repeated three times
152 for each dish. The essential information of each dish is presented in Table I.

153

154 *2.2. Procedure of energy cost tests*

155 In this research, it has been monitored the temperature, time, electrical grid parameters, in order
156 to obtain the different times of cooking in the different dishes, the energy consumption and cost to
157 the user. For the LPG based cooker, the weight of the gas cylinder was measured before, during, and
158 after the cooking processes. The energy consumption is represented by the equation [1], when
159 considering 13005 kcal/kg as heat of combustion, given by the Quito gas distributor.

160

$$161 \quad E [kWh] = \frac{\Delta m * PCs}{860} \quad [1]$$

162

163 Where

164 E : is the consumed energy [kWh]

165 Δm : ($m_f - m_i$) is the mass variation of P in [kg].

166 PCs : is the heat of combustion of LPG in [kcal/kg]

167 It was applied a conversion factor between 1 kWh and its equivalent of 860 kcal (31)

168 When energy consumption values were measured, the cost of the energy was calculated taking
169 into account a price of \$ 0,09 per kWh for the electricity and \$ 20 for a 15 kg cylinder of LPG (32),
170 (33). These prices were selected considering the price of the electricity in a house in Ecuador and the
171 internacional price of a LPG cylinder.

172 For electric measurements in the electric and induction cookers, the Fluke 430 TF II and the
173 analyzer Sentron PAC3200 of Siemens have been placed on the wires of the electric grid to measure
174 its parameters such as current and voltage. The temperature of the food and time cooking were
175 measured too.

176

177 *2.3. Procedure of CO and CO₂ tests*

178 In this study indoor air quality analyzer Brain Bee Au Mobile complete mobile unit has been used
179 for emission control to measure the indoor CO and CO₂ concentrations. The range of CO₂
180 measurement is from 0 ppm to 15000 ppm with an accuracy of 1 ppm, and the response time is 1 s.
181 The range of CO measurement is from 0 ppm to 500 ppm with an accuracy of 0,01 ppm, and the
182 response time is 1 s.

183 The experimental process for measuring the CO and CO₂ emissions during cooking was the
184 following: first, it has been closed the interior door and the exterior window, and we turned on the
185 exhaust hood. Then we placed the measuring sensors at the breathing zone of a person (145 cm) in
186 order to measure the background levels of the kitchen indoor environment for a period of 60 s. After
187 that, we started cooking one of the four case-study dishes of Ecuadorian cuisines and continued
188 measuring the air concentrations of CO and CO₂. A sample was collected outdoor. When the cooking
189 process was finished, we continuously measured the parameters until the concentrations in the kitchen
190 reestablished at an acceptable level. Between each experiment, the cookware was washed thoroughly
191 with copious amounts of warm water and with detergent repeatedly.

192

193 ***2.4. Organoleptic measurement***

194 The discriminative triangular test was used for determining the differences in the consumers
195 perception between samples made with induction and LPG based cookers. One hundred seven people
196 from National Institute for Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy of Ecuador (INER) participated
197 (without restrictions or food allergy). They have not been trained in sensory evaluation. In addition,
198 the degrees of difference and acceptance (affective test) were made (34).

199 In practice three samples were presented to each panelist, two were alike, one was different. The
200 panelist was asked to select the odd sample. The six possible sequences of two dishes were distributed
201 five times in each panel, as shown in Table II. The samples were evaluated from the left to the right.
202 The food taste was developed between 15:00 and 17:00 in 5 dishes: grilled chicken, steamed fish,
203 cooked broccoli, little orange with oatmeal drink and Russian salad. The samples were served as soon
204 as the cooking process finished, at temperatures and habitual conditions of consumption. Food was
205 served in plastic containers of similar characteristics, in portions of 15 g and 25 ml.

206 To reduce errors in the results, the panel members were asked to avoid the use of substances with
207 strong odors (soaps, lotions and perfumes), besides, they did not eat or drink (except water) nor smoke
208 at least 30 minutes before the taste. The evaluation methodology was explained in a written and oral
209 way during the taste. The statistics interpretation of these results was made following the
210 methodologies of Anzaldúa (34) and British Standard ISO 4120:2004 (35).

211

212 ***2.5. Physicochemical and microbiological measurements***

213 Food samples of the three cookers were taken as soon as the cooking process finished for making
214 proximate and microbiological analysis. These samples were analyzed by the accredited laboratory

215 with certify number OAE LE C 09-008. The results were compared with values established in national
216 and international standards in table III (36), (37), (38), (39), (40), (41).

217

218 **3. Results**

219 In this section the results of the energy consumption, concentrations of CO and CO₂, organoleptic,
220 physicochemical and microbiological measurements are presented.

221

222 **3.1. Results of energy measurements.**

223 The cooking process information is showed in table IV. For the LPG cooker, it has been observed
224 that the cooking time increased between 20 % and 396 % with respect to the induction cooker
225 depending on the dish. This time reduction is related, in most of the cases, to the steps 1 of table I,
226 which are the heating processes of water or oil. Energy consumption was reduced by induction cooker
227 between 44 % and 170 % with respect to LPG cookers. As energy consumption is reduced, also the
228 cost for the final user is reduced. A reduction between 41 % and 167 % was found when comparing
229 the induction cooker with the LPG based cooker, considering the real price of the LPG without subsidy.

230 In addition, it has been observed, that the cooking time was reduced between 200 % and 1700 %
231 for the induction cooker with respect to the electric cooker. This increment in time is clearly related
232 to the low power of the electric cooker, which was 500 W at the higher hob and 300 W at the smaller
233 hob, as it showed in figure 2. The energy consumption was reduced in the induction cooker between
234 24 % and 80% with respect to the electric cooker. It was observed an increment in cost to the user by
235 the electric cookers between 24 and 80 % with respect to the induction cooker.

236 The induction cooker was more efficient than the electric and LPG based cookers, because
237 induction cooker reduced the cooking time and the energy consumption which contributes to

238 minimize the cost to the user. Nevertheless, currently in Ecuador, this price of LPG is twelve times
239 lower (32), (33). For this reason, users have the perception that cooking with a LPG cooker is less
240 costly than cooking with an induction cooker.

241 Figure 2 shows the plots of the variations of active power during cooking in electric and induction
242 cooker and LPG cooker. Variable active power behavior during cooking in induction and LPG cookers
243 can be seen in Figure 2. For the induction cooker it was the first time that the chefs used the cooker,
244 for this reason some peaks appeared in the plots. In case of the electric resistance cooker the power is
245 constant for most of the cooking processes, because during the preparation of the dishes, the electric
246 resistance cooker is working most of the time close to its maximum power or the maximum power of
247 each hob.

248

249 *3.2. Results of CO and CO₂ measurements*

250 Figure 3 presents the variations of CO and CO₂ concentrations during cooking in a LPG, induction
251 and electric resistance cookers. In case of the electric and the induction cooker, the CO and CO₂
252 concentrations remained low, as expected. In case of the LPG cooker, the results depend on the type
253 of dish

254

255 **3.2.1. Hard boiled eggs**

256 As soon as the LPG based cooker was turned on and the water was added (step 1 from the table I),
257 the concentrations of CO and CO₂ increased during cooking hard boiled eggs, as can be seen in Figure
258 3 a)-b). Concentrations of CO in the idle mode reached 13 ppm which is 3 ppm (30 %) higher than the
259 acceptable value (42), (43), (44). In the working mode CO concentrations achieved a peak value of 8,5
260 ppm. In the idle mode concentrations of CO₂ reached 2200 ppm which is 1200 ppm (120 %) higher

261 than the acceptable value, meanwhile in the working mode the concentrations achieved a peak value
262 of 1200 ppm which is 200 ppm (20 %) higher of than the acceptable value.

263 When the egg was added (step 2 from the table I), active power during cooking have been
264 decreased. For this reason, concentrations of CO and CO₂ in the LPG cooker decreased. In case of CO
265 concentrations, they decreased under the acceptable values in idle and working mode. In case of CO₂
266 concentrations, the decreased under the acceptable values for the working mode, but CO₂
267 concentrations remained constant for the idle mode.

268

269 **3.2.2. Grilled chicken**

270 While cooking grilled chicken (Figure 3 c)-d)), the LPG cooker was turned on and the oil was added
271 (step 1 from the table I), the concentrations of CO in the idle mode reached 18 ppm which is 8 ppm
272 (80 %) higher than the acceptable value. In the working mode CO concentrations achieved a peak
273 value of 13 ppm. In the idle mode concentrations of CO₂ reached 2000 ppm, meanwhile in the working
274 mode the concentrations achieved a peak value of 1200 ppm which is 200 ppm (20 %) higher of than
275 the acceptable value.

276 When the chicken was added (step 2 from the table I), the active power during cooking have been
277 remained constant. Concentrations of CO and CO₂ in the LPG based cooker increased in the idle mode.
278 CO concentrations achieved a peak value of 23 ppm, which is 13 ppm (130 %) higher than the
279 acceptable value. In contrast, in working mode, they decreased under the acceptable values. In case of
280 CO₂ concentrations, they reached 3600 ppm in the idle mode which is 2600 ppm (260 %) higher than
281 the acceptable value and 1600 ppm in the working mode.

282

283 **3.2.3. Milk**

284 During cooking milk the process took 83 s (Figure 3 e)-f)). Consequently, the concentrations of CO
285 and CO₂ increased during the whole process, but they did not exceed the acceptable values.

286

287 **3.2.4. Boiled chochos**

288 When cooking boiled chochos (Figure 3 g)-h)), the active power remained constant during the test.
289 So concentrations of CO increased during the test until 9 ppm. In the working mode CO concentrations
290 increased during the test until 4 ppm. In case of the concentrations of CO₂, they reached 1300 ppm in
291 the idle mode which is 300 ppm (30 %) higher than the acceptable value. For the working mode CO₂
292 concentrations achieved 900 ppm.

293

294 **3.2.5. Steamed fish**

295 As soon as the LPG based cooker was turned on during cooking steamed fish (Figure 3 i)-j)), and
296 the water was added (step 1 from the table I), the concentrations of CO and CO₂ increased.
297 Concentrations of CO in the idle mode reached 15 ppm which is 5 ppm (50 %) higher than the
298 acceptable value. In the working mode concentrations of CO reached a peak value of 12 ppm. In the
299 idle mode concentrations of CO₂ reached 2500 ppm, which is 1500 ppm (150 %) higher than the
300 acceptable value, meanwhile in the working mode the concentrations achieved a peak value of 850
301 ppm.

302 When the fish was added (step 2 from the table I), the active power remained constant. In case of
303 CO concentrations, they increased in the idle mode until 16 ppm and they decreased in the working
304 mode until 11 ppm. In case of CO₂ concentrations, they increased in the idle mode until 2600 ppm and
305 they increased in the working mode until 900 ppm.

306

307 **3.2.6. Boiled broccoli**

308 While cooking boiled broccoli (Figure 3 k-l)), the active power remained constant during the test.
309 For this reason, concentrations of CO remained within the acceptable values. During the test they
310 reached 9,2 ppm in the idle mode and 6,8 ppm in the working mode. In case of concentrations of CO₂,
311 they reached 1500 ppm in the idle mode which is 500 ppm (50 %) higher than the acceptable value
312 and 900 ppm for the working mode.

313

314 **3.2.7. Little orange with oatmeal drink**

315 While cooking the orange with oatmeal drink (Figure 3 m-n)), when the cooker was turned on and
316 the water, and the oatmeal and orange were added (step 1 from the table I). Concentrations of CO in
317 the idle mode reached 13,2 ppm which is 3,2 ppm (32 %) higher than the acceptable value. In the
318 working mode CO concentrations achieved a peak value of 7 ppm. In the idle mode concentrations of
319 CO₂ reached 2550 ppm, which is 1550 ppm (155 %) higher of than the acceptable value. Meanwhile,
320 in the working mode the concentrations achieved a peak value of 1200 ppm. After 800 s, of cooking
321 in figure 2-g) is showed that the active power during cooking decreased; consequently, concentrations
322 of CO and CO₂ decreased until acceptable values.

323

324

325 **3.2.8. Boiled carrots,**

326 As soon as the cooker was turned on during cooking of the boiled carrots (Figure 3 o-p)), when
327 the water with carrots were added (step 1 from the table I), the concentrations of CO and CO₂ increased.
328 Concentrations of CO in the idle mode reached 11 ppm which is 1 ppm (10 %) higher than the
329 acceptable value. Although, in the working mode CO concentrations achieved a peak value of 8 ppm.

330 In the idle mode concentrations of CO₂ reached 1350 ppm, which is 350 ppm (35 %) higher than
331 the acceptable value, meanwhile in the working mode the concentrations achieved a peak value of 900
332 ppm.

333 In figure 2-h) is showed that after 800 s of cooking the active power decreases. For this reason,
334 concentrations of CO and CO₂ decreased until acceptable values.

335

336 **3.2.9. Boiled potatoes**

337 During cooking boiled potatoes (Figure 3 q)-r)), the active power remained at 850 W in the LPG
338 cooker during the test. For this reason, concentrations of CO have ben remained into the acceptable
339 values. During the test they reached 8 ppm in the idle mode and 5,6 ppm in the working mode. In case
340 of concentrations of CO₂, they reached 770 ppm in the idle mode and 75 ppm for the working mode.

341

342 **3.2.10. Boiled peas**

343 While cooking the boiled peas (Figure 3 s)-t)), the active power remained at 675 W during the test.
344 Consequently, concentrations of CO remained within the acceptable values. During the test they
345 reached 7 ppm in the idle mode and 5 ppm in the working mode. In case of concentrations of CO₂,
346 they reached 720 ppm in the idle mode and 700 ppm for the working mode.

347

348

349 ***3.3. Results of the organoleptic measurement***

350 The results of the sensory evaluation are showed in Table V. A total of one hundred seven panelists
351 participated in the taste, they determined a significantly difference ($\alpha=0,001$) in little orange with
352 oatmeal, grilled chicken, steamed fish and broccoli and it was not perceptible in Russian salad, which
353 were cooking with the same methodology in induction and LPG based cookers. The degree of

354 difference in these four dishes was moderate. Three of the four dishes cooked with induction cooker
355 were more acceptable than that one's cooked with the LPG based cooker ($\alpha=0,05$). In the other dish
356 appeared equally acceptable when cooked in the induction cooker and in the LPG based cooker.

357

358 ***3.4. Results of Physicochemical and microbiological measurement***

359 Table VI shows the results that are outside the range, obtained before and after the thermal
360 treatment. The used references were found in national standards, books and nutrition fact tables of
361 the macronutrients containing in food as Table VII shows (12), (39), (40), (38), (51), (13), and (52)
362 except for Russian salad and the little orange with oatmeal drink. Only milk and chochos references
363 had concentration ranges. For milk, hard-boiled eggs and boiled broccoli a comparative range of \pm
364 10 % of the reference value was defined.

365 The microbiological and physicochemical changes produced by thermal treatment in food are
366 described in table VII and table VIII. The analyzed micronutrients were vitamin C in broccoli and
367 vitamin A in egg, broccoli and Russian salad. Both of them present moderate sensitivity to heat (45).
368 After the thermal treatment, it was observed that vitamin C lost in similar quantities in the three types
369 of cookware, while vitamin A lost in less quantity when using the induction cooker. The vitamin A
370 lost was reduced by induction cooker between 160 % and 471 % less than the LPG based cookers
371 and between 41 % and 546 % less than the electric cookers

372 In order to evaluate the microbiological load, national standards were used, as shown in Table VII.
373 Only for the milk and the fish, requirements for before and after of the thermal treatment were found.
374 The milk and the chicken, as feedstock, are above of the allowed concentrations during total recount
375 of bacteria. After the thermal treatment the total bacteria concentration in the boiled milk in the LPG
376 based cooker does not meet the requirements, the other samples of microbiological load of spoilage
377 and pathogenic decreases to concentrations that are not harmful for human health.

379 **4. Discussion**

380 Different from several former researchers (46), (47) and same than other studies (48), (49), we
381 found the cooking techniques in an LPG based cooker, like boiling or frying is the one to blame to
382 increase the emissions of CO and CO₂. Furthermore, the tests showed how the frying process increased
383 the concentrations of CO, CO₂. The emissions of CO and CO₂ not only were related to the cooking
384 time, but also occurred largely as a result of the burning of the LPG. Consequently, the higher calorific
385 power used in the LPG cooker during cooking, the larger of CO₂ was generated. When the frying oil
386 was added into the dish, the maximum emissions of CO and CO₂ during cooking this kind of dishes is
387 at least 138 % higher than the others in CO emissions and 135 % higher than the others in CO₂
388 emissions, in case of the idle mode at the hood. For this reason, it is necessary to seek more effective
389 solutions like the working mode of the hood, or other. A LPG based cooker increases the
390 concentrations of CO and CO₂ during the preparation of the food. Indeed, they exceed the maximum
391 levels of volatile emissions acceptable into buildings (42), (43), (44). On the other hand, electrical and
392 induction cookers kept the concentrations within the acceptable levels. Moreover, it was observed that
393 the induction cooker improves user quality of life. It has been observed that the production of carbon
394 dioxide and carbon monoxide decreases indoors for this reason it could be sold a cleaner technology.

395 The values of test parameters finally reached a stable value after a certain period of time. It should
396 be noted that many families in Ecuador do not have an exhaust hood. Consequently, the emissions of
397 CO and CO₂ during cooking would be higher.

398 The results of the cooking process, which has considered the cooking habits of the Ecuadorian
399 cuisine, concludes that induction cookers decreased the energy cost between 24 and 80 %, when its
400 compared with electric cookers. This increment in of the electric cooker with respect of the induction
401 cooker time is clearly related to the low power of the electric cooker, which was 500 W at its peak

402 when is working the higher hob. In case of the LPG based cooker the energy cost for was increased
403 between 41 % and 167 %, when it is compared with induction cookers, considering a price for the 15
404 kg LPG cylinder of \$ 20.00, which is the price in neighbors' countries of Ecuador. In contrast, currently
405 in Ecuador, this price is twelve times lower and users have the misconception that cooking with a LPG
406 based cooker is cheaper than cooking with an induction cooker. For the electric cooker, the energy
407 consumption was reduced by the induction cooker with respect to the electric cooker.

408 The temperature and cooking time of food are influenced by the atmospheric pressure that is
409 inversely proportional to the height above sea level (50). Therefore, the results of this study are
410 specific for highlands. All kind of food has water in its chemical composition and is it mostly cooked
411 in aqueous media. Finish cooking in highlands takes longer than in other cities due to the heat at
412 thermal treatment is reached at less temperature. With these conditions, volatile organic compounds
413 contained in food are easy to escape, even before of the thermal treatment and have a direct influence
414 with the flavor lost (50), which represent the complex set of olfactory and taste properties perceived
415 during tasting (51).

416 The organoleptic test was performed without experienced judges because INER researchers do
417 not have a tasting training. However, for this test it was enough for the panelists to be usual consumers
418 and to be familiar with the five dishes. This fact increased the likelihood of finding a significant
419 difference in the samples (35).

420 The Russian salad and the little orange with oatmeal drink were the dishes more complex because
421 in both of them several elements are mixed. The Russian salad is a solid-solid mixture and the little
422 orange with oatmeal drink is a solid-liquid mixture. These dishes were cooked and presented as
423 homogeneously as possible. Between the five evaluated dishes, only the Russian salad did not present
424 a significant difference in the discriminative triangular test. Usually, the solid mixtures are less
425 homogeneously. It is because of this principle that no difference was detected in the Russian salad
426 samples. On the other hand, the affective test shows that food cooked in induction cooker present a

427 higher acceptance in the consumers, except for the steamed fish. In this research, the panelists are
428 able to detect difference and accept the food cooked in both cookers. This sensory test indirectly
429 measures the induction cookers acceptance.

430 The nutritional quality of any kind of food depends on the thermal treatment used. The usual
431 chemical and physical changes are presented in Table VIII. The energy intake does not get affected
432 because the macronutrients are lost in a lower quantity. Generally, vitamins and minerals vanish.
433 These food components do not supply energy to human body, but they are essential in every chemical
434 reaction that produces energy (13). The chemical composition of any kind of food can be modified
435 for changes in weather conditions, soil type (in vegetables) and feeding type (in animals). A change
436 in these conditions could have modified the chemical composition of analyzed food. It is for this
437 reason that some products are outside the reference range.

438 On the other hand, the thermal treatment used in the three cookers decreased the microbiological
439 load to the acceptable levels, except for milk boiled in the LPG based cooker, where the total bacterial
440 count is higher than the quality requirement established in the standard NTE INEN 10:2012 (37).
441 There was likely a contamination during sampling and/or analysis, which might have changed was
442 determinant to modify the results. Despite having different cooking times, the three kinds of cookers
443 guarantee the food safety as shown in Table VII.

444

445 **5. Conclusions**

446 The results of the cooking process information, concludes that in the LPG based cooker the time,
447 energy consumption, and cost were higher with respect to the induction cooker. The time reduction
448 is related with the heating processes of water or oil. The reduction in energy consumption and cost is
449 related to the higher energy efficiency of the induction cooker. In the electric cooker the cooking

450 time, energy consumption, and cost were higher with respect to the induction cooker. The increment
451 in time is related to the low power of the electric cooker, and the energy consumption and cost are
452 due to the energy efficiency of the cooker.

453 The results concluded that during cooking the case study of the dishes of eight cuisines of Ecuador,
454 concentration of CO and CO₂, increased during the entire process. In the whole process, it has been
455 observed that the LPG based cooker, the concentrations of CO and CO₂ in hood idle mode and
456 working mode have been increased over the acceptable values. Furthermore, it can be seen that the
457 maximum values of the contaminants appear during grilled chicken with achiote oil in the hood idle
458 mode. In contrast electric and induction cookers keep low CO and CO₂ concentration, as expected
459 and they do not exceed the acceptable values.

460 Food flavor does not change; it is lost due to the height above sea level, temperature and cooking
461 time. In Quito, the panelists detected the difference between food cooked in induction cooker and
462 LPG based cooker. The degree of difference is moderate (comparing it with the same dishes cooked
463 in the LPG based cooker); besides, food cooked in induction cookers present more acceptance.

464 The microbiological analysis showed that the pathogens and spoilage present in the food cooked
465 in the three types of cooker are reduced to concentrations no harmful to human health. The vitamin
466 A lost in less quantity in food cooked in induction cookers than electric and LPG based cooker, while
467 vitamin C lost in similar quantities when cooking in any of the cookers. The chemical composition
468 of some food (feedstock and finished product) are outside the reference range described in standards,
469 books and nutrition facts tables (38), (39), (40), (12), (51), (13), and (52).

470 The study concluded that the positive aspects in induction cookers are: i) efficiency in cooking
471 time, energy consumption and cost, ii) no emission of harmful concentrations of CO and CO₂, iii)
472 the food cooked is more acceptable, iv) less quantity of vitamin A losses, vi) high food safety.

473

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481

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